

A Comprehensive Document Analysis of Green Infrastructure Case Studies in the Global South

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Abstract

With the rapid pace of urbanization and increasing environmental challenges, it is crucial to prioritize the adoption of sustainable practices. Unfortunately, these practices are often considered a privilege restricted to wealthy communities. The negative consequences of this inequality are experienced mostly in countries situated in the Global South. These countries are often categorized as developing countries and low-income areas, making them the most vulnerable to natural hazards. This study undertakes a document analysis approach for green infrastructure practices in urban areas of the Global South. Using a document analysis technique, it integrates findings from 20 case studies and highlights common challenges and recommendations. The selection criteria for the case study analysis focused on public engagement and perception, as community-driven projects tend to have better long-term outcomes. Given that most countries in the Global South are affected by natural hazards, it is important to raise awareness of green infrastructure projects and emphasize cost-effective, community-driven initiatives. The purpose of this research is to serve as a foundation for future primary research or case studies, and encourage governments and stakeholders to prioritize the implementation of sustainable practices in these vulnerable regions.

Keywords: Low-income areas, green infrastructure, Global South, community, public engagement

1. Introduction

Just recently, there has been a growing consciousness regarding the construction of our urban areas. The increased impervious land areas as a result of urbanization are causing multiple problems such as runoff control. The increase in runoff can result in a higher frequency of floods and a reduction in base flows [1]. Moreover, the emergence of ecological issues many of which are related to climate change demanded a shift towards implementing green infrastructure as an alternative solution for stormwater management. Green infrastructure mimics the natural hydrological system that aligns with the surrounding ecosystem by increasing the capacity for capturing and retaining stormwater volume in urban watersheds. Green infrastructure includes various installations such as rain gardens, green roofs, constructed wetlands, pervious pavement, and bioswales all of which serve as beneficial landscape products[2,3]. Besides these ecological benefits, there are social benefits that green infrastructure can provide, for example, more access to nature can be conceived and learning opportunities about such ecological tools. Despite some studies indicating public acceptance of such tools in particular stormwater infiltration, there is a limited number of studies regarding their engagement and perceiving these tools as part of nature [4]. The majority of the research regarding this topic is located in the global North. Therefore, this study will contribute to investigating more public involvement in urban areas that are low-income and mainly situated in the Global South. Most regions in the Global South are labeled as developing countries and they are mostly at greater risk of natural hazards like flooding. This research sheds light on public engagement with green infrastructure in low-income, developing countries of the Global South. Understanding their perspectives is crucial for designing cost-effective and socially acceptable green solutions for flood mitigation and improved urban living.

It is worth mentioning that prior research examined public knowledge perception regarding green infrastructure specifically for flood management conducted by Venkataraman et al. [5]. Their work identified 85 studies but it is mainly concentrated in developed countries with 59% of the studies situated in the U.S. only a limited number of case studies focused on the Global South. This imbalance underscores the need for further investigation into public knowledge and engagement surrounding green infrastructure projects in developing regions. Valuable conclusions from their study showed that knowledge and awareness of green infrastructure were low; attitudes were measured; and willingness to

implement or pay for green infrastructure projects varied. Other factors that are important to consider prior knowledge are age, income, ownership, and race. Additionally, there is a huge willingness to implement green infrastructure measures if provided or with a saving however, their experience with stormwater issues suggests a potential openness to green infrastructure solutions, even with limited prior knowledge. Their study indicated that females showed more willingness than males to implement green infrastructure installations by 2.7 times more.

2. General Analysis of Green Infrastructure in the Global South

2.1. The Term Application

The Global South accounts for three regions: Africa, Asia, and Latin America, sharing relatively similar challenges. While awareness of green infrastructure is growing, the concept is relatively new in many countries of the Global South. However, the full implementation of green infrastructure is yet to be embraced by both governments and citizens, with more progress needed in this regard. Green infrastructure can have different names and interpretations. In all three regions, there is a strong emphasis on single green space types like urban parks, gardens, and forests, both in research and practical applications. This is noticeable in Asia, where a significant amount of literature has explored various green and blue space types. Moreover, it is hard to comprehend the state of green infrastructure in this region due to its wide diversity, and the amount of research conducted outside of China and India as China stands out as a prominent figure in sustainable development that incorporates key principles of green infrastructure into its statutory planning [6]. The term green infrastructure in China is used as an urban green space system whereas in Malaysia is a green network. On the other hand, the term urban green system is often studied in big to middle cities like Beijing, Shanghai, Nanjing, Shenzhen, and Guangzhou [7]. In Dhaka, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka, green infrastructure is seen as a strategic approach to identifying challenges encountered by those living in slum areas [8,9]. In Africa, green infrastructure is often referred to as urban forest, urban green structure, urban forest and metropolitan open space systems, bio-infrastructure and ecological infrastructure [10–12]. Most studied green infrastructure projects in Latin America include urban forests and green spaces. In Colombia, the term has been used as the ecological main structure [13,14].

2.2. Major Challenges for the Development of Green Infrastructure

The varying understandings of green infrastructure can further complicate addressing the challenges posed by rapid urbanization in the Global South. It is estimated that the urban population worldwide will experience a significant growth of 2.5 billion individuals. Asia and Africa will account for nearly 90% of this growth [15]. Areas within those regions tend to have accelerated urbanization processes and this affects the development of green infrastructure due to insufficient planning, limited opportunities for supervision or enforcement, and most critically lack of funding for the construction and maintenance of green infrastructure [16,17]. According to the United Nations Latin America is considered the highest urbanized region as 80% of the population lives in urban areas and is anticipated to rise to 85% by the year 2040 [15]. This growth resulted in a significant decline in green areas, primarily due to the transformation of farmland and natural habitats into urban environments [18]. Latin America is home to some of the most biodiverse regions in the world, making the impacts on natural ecosystems particularly significant as they are crucial for the preservation of various species and their habitats [23]. Parallel to this, Latin America holds real estate megaprojects for high-income residency and that creates a new urban periphery dominated by corporate control [24]. The issue with this is the outskirts of most Latin American cities are often slums or low-income settlements. These areas lack vegetation, have limited biodiversity, and are susceptible to various risks such as floods, landslides, and industrial pollution [25,26]. Therefore, it is advised in the case of Latin America any planning program to include forms of environmental justice [13]. On the other hand, the problem of urban growth can be reflected in flooding and drainage problems in Sub-Saharan African cities [19–21]. The major characteristics of urbanization in Africa are uncontrolled urban expansion and the remnants of colonial influence that can be reflected in the levels of informality and the lack of proper urban planning [22].

Affordability is a significant challenge for low-income societies when it comes to acquiring new green tools. These tools are often associated with expensive technologies, making them difficult for low-income communities to adopt. However, promoting the widespread use of green infrastructure requires cost-effective solutions. Recent studies suggest that nature-based solutions can be low-cost and adaptable to any location, and should be considered by authorities [27]. It's important to remember that "low cost" doesn't equate to lower quality. Effective strategies for promoting green infrastructure in low-

income communities can include informing and educating the public about the advantages of these tools. Additionally, incorporating policies that enhance ecological life and biodiversity can be implemented [28]. A study conducted by Fluhrer et al. [29] identified three key aspects to be priorities when looking for feasible solutions: hydrological, ecological, and social dimensions. By implementing such technologies on a larger scale within urban areas, rather than solely at the individual household level, cities can improve their overall health and positively impact the well-being of their residents [30].

2.3. Urban Planning Policies in the Global South

A major problem most developing countries have is the lack of political support which results in, technical ability, and educational policies [31]. These challenges are reflected in collaborative work between various sectors within an institutional structure. Moreover, it is essential to have a comprehensive understanding of citizens' perceptions of the values and services provided by green infrastructure to effectively promote its implementation [32]. In Latin America, the integration of green infrastructure into urban planning schemes is progressing at a slow pace [13]. Whereas in Sub-Saharan African city planning schemes lack clearness and strategic implementation since most information is out of date specifically regarding land use and future urban growth patterns, thus affecting the consideration of green infrastructure elements [23,33]. As mentioned before, China has strong planning strategies that implement green infrastructure; this is reflected in five domains of urban green spaces: public parks, nurseries, green buffers, and attached green spaces. In recent years, there has been a rise in the development of new types of green spaces including country parks, wetland parks, mining brownfield parks, and landfill parks [34–36]. In 2014, China implemented a nationwide initiative called "Sponge City Construction" in response to the growing awareness of climate change impacts. This program aimed to address various stormwater challenges, including pluvial flooding, water pollution, water resources scarcity, and the provision of ecosystem services [37,38]. China's adoption of the "Sponge City" concept as a strategic approach to stormwater management has not only distinguished itself but also had a significant influence on neighboring countries.

2.4. Awareness and Knowledge of Green Infrastructure

Community-initiated activities have shown their potential in creating and sustaining urban green infrastructure across all three regions of the Global South. Examples of such activities include community gardens and the reforestation of slopes prone to hazards [39–41]. These initiatives have proven to be effective in enhancing green infrastructure projects and can serve as successful models for other communities to follow. However, the lack of communication and collaboration between city governments and local communities is still a widespread issue in all three regions, as highlighted in the studies [25,33]. Active participation of local communities and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) from the initial stages is crucial to minimize possible conflicts, as emphasized by Adegun [42] and Douglas [21]. Green infrastructure development in socio-economically disadvantaged communities seems to be overlooked in urban policies. While residents in these areas often highly value and utilize green spaces, government-led initiatives may not always fully understand their needs and desires [43]. Examples like the Victor Jara Park in Santiago and the reforestation initiative in Rio de Janeiro highlight this challenge [41]. The lack of social inclusion is closely linked to issues of environmental justice, particularly in Latin America, where access and quality of green spaces can be unequal. The availability of trees in both public and private areas is also significant, especially for Indigenous communities with strong connections to specific green infrastructure elements [44,45]. However, projects like the Iguacu project serve as cautionary tales, highlighting that green infrastructure implementation can have unintended consequences. Evicting informal settlers from flood-prone areas, for example, disrupts their social and economic well-being [21]. Despite these challenges, there are positive signs. A study in South Africa found that a significant number of residents own private gardens and trees, fostering a flourishing green industry with job opportunities and knowledge generation [46].

On a broader note, limited understanding of public perceptions regarding the environment hinders progress in environmental protection programs across Sub-Saharan Africa [47]. Studies in Ethiopia highlight similar challenges, including lack of community participation, limited professional skills, budget constraints, and poor interdepartmental coordination [48]. Furthermore, the exclusion of poor residents in informal settlements from the planning process leads to the fragmentation of green spaces and the loss of valuable ecosystem services they rely on [43].

3. Discussion

Public awareness regarding green infrastructure is still low, and raising awareness should be considered within planning agendas because informing the public about green tools and climate change issues helps tremendously the well-being of communities. When conveying such ideas to the public, it is important to consider the financial aspects as people need incentives because their economics determine their willingness to participate in green infrastructure projects. Based on the literature review, public engagement in green infrastructure projects was mainly conducted in wealthy communities located in the global north, this means high-income communities typically possess the means to provide better living conditions and public amenities [27,50]. This overall enables these communities to be more equipped to handle natural hazards. While low-income areas usually characterized by an uncontrolled process of urbanization tend to have many sustainability challenges and, therefore more vulnerable to natural hazards.

4. Materials and Method

The qualitative research approach employed a document analysis method to conduct this search. The research criteria focused on green infrastructure case studies situated in the Global South, specifically in developing countries and low-income areas, including keywords like public perception, knowledge, beliefs, attitudes, involvement, and community engagement. The materials used for this research were secondary research obtained from existing literature, with English as the search language—the research criteria centered on the social dimension and public attitudes toward green infrastructure. The scope of the research primarily involved internet-based literature from journals. A selection of 20 case studies that met the criteria were examined and the data was then categorized into a pre-defined set of variables in order to extract findings and conclusions. These variables were: country, region, the type of green infrastructure (e.g., parks, green roofs, rain gardens, or not specified), public engagement (e.g., consultations, participatory planning, survey answers), stakeholders as in the groups involved in the study (e.g., NGOs, Governmental bodies), public perception meaning the project impact on the community and the public general impressions (positive, negative, mixed), the challenges faced in the case study/ limitations (e.g., lack of funding and lastly the key takeaways or recommendations/insights derived from the case study. To facilitate comparison, the data from the case studies was consolidated into a single table Figure [1,2], allowing for a clear overview of the different variables.

5. Integrating the Findings

Community engagement and participation are crucial factors influencing public perception of green infrastructure projects. Studies indicate that positive perceptions are closely linked to strong community involvement, particularly where residents are engaged in the planning, implementation, and maintenance of projects. Such inclusive public engagement strategies foster a sense of ownership and long-term commitment, which are essential for the success of these initiatives.

No.	Case Study Title	country/city	Green Infrastructure Type	Public Engagement	Stakeholders	Public Perception	Challenges	Key Take aways	other
1	How Medellin is beating the heat with green corridors	Columbia/ Medellin	green corridors	municipal participatory budget that allows residents to choose initiatives for funding.	local government, researchers at the University of Antioquia, and community members who participated in maintenance and volunteered as gardeners.	positive/ People also participated in the project's maintenance.	initial investment and ongoing maintenance costs, air pollution	The Medellin project demonstrates the effectiveness in reducing urban heat island effect, improving air quality and enhancing biodiversity. The project also highlights the importance of public engagement and participation for the success of such initiatives.	https://www.bbc.com/future/article
2	On the Sabarmati Riverfront: Urban Planning as Totalitarian Governance in Ahmedabad	India/ Ahmedabad	urban landscaping project, will include urban parks	participatory forums and dialogic engagement with the project's unfolding	governmental bodies, private actors, community groups, civil society, and academic institutions	multifaceted, with academic critiques emerging and public hearings attended by over 500 people, leading to a favorable judgment in the public interest	poverty, inequity, and exclusionary planning processes complex political factors, local circumstances, and patterns of urban development.	the expansive space of action available to interested private experts, academic critiques, and the role of alternative experts in the project	
3	The challenge of urban poverty for the use of green infrastructure on floodplains and wetlands to reduce flood impacts in intertropical Africa	Burkina Faso/ Bobo-Dioulasso	greenways, green open spaces, peri-urban forests, and traditional market gardens	participatory planning and consultations	political actors, technical experts, civil society, opinion leaders, local residents, and international organizations	positive	understanding local environmental processes, people's livelihoods, and political relationships between various levels of government and different parts of complex urban communities	the importance of holistic views across all scales of the political, social, economic, and environmental aspects of intertropical African cities to make real progress in flood hazard reduction	
4	Social perceptions of the value of green spaces: A view from the South	South Africa	evaluating green spaces	survey-based study involving professionals working in the Built Environment in South Africa.	professionals working in the Built Environment in South Africa	majority perceived population growth as the greatest urban risk, with a limited recognition of environmental degradation	development pressures, budget constraints, and fast-changing societal needs, along with the subjective valuation of green spaces	social perceptions should be comprehensively understood, especially in the quest of realizing greener spaces and cities in the Global South //” environmental awareness lecture on the value of green spaces: This lecture was part of the research design, and the survey	The study aimed to investigate how individuals view urban risks and priorities, the value of urban green spaces, along with their appreciation and use of such spaces

5	Rethinking urban green infrastructure and ecosystem services from the perspective of sub-Saharan African cities	Adis Ababa, Ethiopia/ Dar es Salaam, Tanzania	not specified	traditional top-down approach to planning in Addis Ababa, where formal housing developments were directed into the process. In Dar es Salaam, communities were involved in the protection of communal green spaces, indicating a form of participatory planning and community engagement	academic 'green teams' in Addis Ababa, and community-based and other organizations in Dar es Salaam	not specified	lack of institutional capacity, poor financial awareness, governance issues, lack of coordination and cooperation among stakeholder groups, and a lack of baseline data to support activities	the need for novel governance frameworks, the importance of multi-functionality, and the potential for local innovation due to existing social norms and rules	The case study also emphasizes the importance of considering the intended audience and purpose of green infrastructure interventions, as well as the need for better integration of green infrastructure into urban development
6	Residents' relationship with green infrastructure in Cosmo City, Johannesburg	South Africa, Johannesburg	domestic gardens, public spaces such as parks, and the green belt along the riparian scale	in-depth semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and transect walks with residents, as well as interviews with key informants at the national and municipal levels	residents, community leaders, and key informants at the national and municipal levels	positive and negative experiences associated with green spaces and natural ecosystems	lack of specific guides, standards, and actions related to green infrastructure, as well as difficulties in financing greening projects within the housing subsidy system	the need to recognize and respond to socio-economic and socio-ecological realities inherent in the ways low-income households relate to green infrastructure at different scales	
7	Reflecting on Green Infrastructure and Spatial Planning in Africa: The Complexities, Perception and the Way Forward	South Africa, Johannesburg, and Klerksdorp, North-West Province	not specified	a detailed community survey conducted with 322 residents of the Fleurhof area in Johannesburg, as well as a survey conducted in Klerksdorp, North-West Province, comparing the perceptions of 20 local community members against that of 20 planning professionals	were not explicitly mentioned	varied, with some participants showing positive perceptions of green infrastructure, while others had a limited understanding of the concept	disproving the green compensation theory and the green proximity principle, as well as the need for context-based planning and the lack of comprehensive inclusion of green infrastructure in urban and regional planning	the importance of context-based planning, the need for more research initiatives, and the necessity to integrate green infrastructure in sustainable development discussions	
8	Residents' Willingness to Participate in Green Infrastructure: Spatial Differences and Influence Factors in Shanghai, China	Shanghai, China	not specified	semi-structured interviews, GIS spatial analysis, and multiple regression to gauge residents' willingness	were not explicitly mentioned	not specified	lack of technology, funding, and regulatory support	the need to enhance public perception of pluvial flood risk and to address the lack of supportive factors for green infrastructure implementation	The study found that gender, education level, and floor were deterministic factors of green infrastructure participation in private space, while building age was a factor in public space.
9	Public Perception of Urban Green Infrastructure Quality in Towns from Southeast Nigeria	Abakiliki, Afikpo, Ikwu, and Uburu in Ebonyi State, Southeast Nigeria	not specified	survey of 513 participants, which included residents and workers in urban areas	were not explicitly mentioned	generally positive, with about 66% of the respondents feeling that the quality of green infrastructure in their locations was generally good/ while 32% said the quality was not good at all.	not explicitly mentioned	the influence of factors such as level of education, age, and marital status on the public perception of urban green infrastructure quality	

Figure 1. Content analysis table for the selected 20 case studies. Created by the authors

Techniques such as participatory planning, community consultations, surveys, and direct involvement of residents in project development are effective in achieving this goal. Furthermore, the visible benefits of green infrastructure, such as aesthetic improvements, recreational spaces, and enhanced environmental conditions, significantly contribute to positive public perception. Well-maintained projects that visibly enhance local conditions tend to be received more favorably by the community. However, negative perceptions can arise from several challenges, including economic pressures and competition for limited resources. In regions where basic needs are unmet, the perceived value of green infrastructure diminishes, leading to skepticism and lack of support. Poor quality green spaces, insufficient maintenance, a lack of awareness and understanding of the benefits of green infrastructure in addition to inadequate resources further create negative views or unfavorable perceptions. This issue can be mitigated through targeted educational programs and awareness campaigns designed to inform and engage the community. Socio-economic realities also play a significant role in shaping public perception. In low-income areas, concerns about livelihoods and the struggle for basic needs can overshadow the environmental benefits of green infrastructure, making it imperative to address these socio-economic factors in project design and implementation.

10	Public Perception on the Role of Urban Green Infrastructure Development and Land Use Management in Rapidly Urbanized Countries: The Case of Hawassa City, Ethiopia	Hawassa, Ethiopia	not specified	participation in green infrastructure development and planning, including maintenance, protection, financial support, and technical support	were not explicitly mentioned	predominantly negative, with the majority of participants being negative perceivers	the loss of urban landscape and ecosystem due to unplanned urban growth, as well as the increasing demand for green infrastructure services and benefits, which put more strain on the environment	the importance of public involvement in urban green space planning and development, as well as the correlation between urban green planning and land use changes	The study found that the chance of being positively perceived increased with higher education levels, income, family size, and participation in public meetings, while it decreased with an increase in marital status and type of employment
11	Public perception and preferences of small urban green infrastructures: A case study in Guangzhou, China	Guangzhou, China	green roof, green wall, and small green lane	a questionnaire survey involving 409 respondents from different neighborhoods	were not explicitly mentioned	positive, with 80% of respondents expressing willingness to pay for using and maintaining these UGIs	air pollution / questionnaire limitation is sampling size, question design, background information provided to the respondents, and payment mechanisms.	education and publicity programs for UGIs should be launched for findings various groups of people	
12	Public perception and preferences of industrial green infrastructure in Northwest China	Lanzhou, Northwest China	not specified	a survey, where respondents residing in neighborhoods surrounding industrial areas	were not explicitly mentioned	positive, with a significant proportion (60%) expressing their willingness to pay for GI promotion	cost, policy, and maintenance considerations	the need for customized planning approaches for IGI promotion, considering diverse demographics, and disseminating GI knowledge through media and local organizations for awareness enhancement	
13	Perceptions and contributions of households towards sustainable urban green infrastructure in Malaysia	Johor Bahru, Malaysia	not specified	a questionnaire survey and observations of how people maintain plants in and around their homes and neighborhoods in parts of Johor Bahru	were not explicitly mentioned	not specified	not clear	households with the least number of plants keep 1-9 species, while those with the highest number keep over 30 plant species. In respect of ecosystem services, the three racial groups maintain plants for aesthetics, culinary, socio-cultural and spiritual purposes.	The study also compared gender, age, and job status of the respondents against 14 variables to determine perceptions on socio-ecological aspects of plant-keeping practices.
14	Citizen Perception of Green Spaces Prioritization in Urban Kenya: The Case of Kisumu City and Eldoret Municipality	Kisumu City and Eldoret, Kenya	not specified	questionnaire interviews with users of green spaces in Kisumu City and Eldoret Municipality. A total of 1090 users of green spaces were randomly selected for interviews to solicit data on their views on the place of green spaces according to their felt needs	were not explicitly mentioned	The public perception of green spaces was that they were ranked last in the scheme of priorities of residents in urban Kenya	the low prioritization given to green space planning due to limited resources being directed to critical areas such as roads, water, sanitation, and recurrent expenditure	the need for citizen sensitization on the value of green spaces, as well as the importance of partnership and networking for the provision of green spaces due to competing interests over limited resources	the study highlights the need for urban planners and policy makers to initiate citizen forums for sensitization of residents on the importance and value of green spaces
15	A bottom-up perspective on green infrastructure in informal settlements: Understanding nature's benefits through lived experiences	Tehran, Iran	not specified	semi-structured interviews with residents to explore their conceptions of ecosystem services provided by green infrastructure	were not explicitly mentioned	positive, as residents recognized and valued the cultural, regulating, supporting, and provisioning services provided by green infrastructure	the residents of informal settlements discussed experiencing hazards such as earthquakes and flooding	the importance of green infrastructure to the quality of life and development priorities identified by residents, as well as the need for planners and urban officials to consider green infrastructure as essential infrastructure for informal areas	They highlighted the importance of green areas in providing passive defense against earthquakes and flood control. Residents also expressed concerns about the lack of accessible public green areas during times of crisis, such as earthquakes
16	A Methodology for Assessing the Implementation Potential for Retrofitted and Multifunctional Urban Green Infrastructure in Public Areas of the Global South	San José, Costa Rica	Roadside greenery, habitat types, and road type upgrading	participatory planning and consultations	not specified	not specified	limited available space for UGI implementation and the need to address specific conditions and physical limitations of UGI development in urban areas of the Global South	UGIs has the potential to improve hydrological, ecological, and social conditions of the site.	
17	An Exploratory Case-Study Approach to Understand Multifunctionality in Urban Green Infrastructure Planning in a South African Context	South Africa	gray-green designed elements, urban agriculture, urban natural remnants, public green space, private green space, and informal green space	direct observations by researchers, discussions in literature, and self-assessment methods	Stakeholders included NGOs, governmental bodies, and urban planners	not specified	the implementation of policies, plans, and regulations	the need to integrate ecological considerations into urban planning practice to promote multifunctionality achieved through green infrastructure planning	
18	Local communities' perceptions and use of urban green infrastructure in two Ethiopian cities: Bahir Dar and Hawassa	Bahir Dar and Hawassa, Ethiopia	various types such as greenways, wetlands, agricultural fields, green roofs, green walls, public green space, allotments, green corridors, street trees, urban forests, and vertical greening	not specified, the study emphasizes the importance of understanding local communities' perceptions	not specified	generally positive	not clear	The results show that people have distinct patterns of usage and positive perceptions towards GI in their respective cities. The regression results indicate that gender, age, accessibility, safety, education level, type of green infrastructure, level of awareness, location, and opportunities for social activities are statistically significant predictors of perception.	The study identifies gender as a statistically significant predictor of perception of green infrastructure
19	Investigating the Barriers to Implementation of Green Roofs in Izmir, Turkey	Izmir, Türkiye	green roofs	not specified, he study emphasized the importance of public awareness and perception of green roofs	government officials from various backgrounds such as architecture, landscape architecture, urban planning, and engineering	generally positive, with some concerns about a lack of awareness and technical knowledge	the cost of installation and maintenance, lack of awareness, and the role of government in adoption	the need for incentives and government policy to support the sector, the importance of public perception and awareness, and the role of government in encouraging the installation of green roofs	
20	Factors influencing residents' attitude towards urban green infrastructure in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria	Lagos, Nigeria	parks, gardens, grasses, sport fields, and street trees (it did not implement rather focused on studying the factors that influenced residents' attitude.	questionnaire survey of 1560 participants and physical observations in selected neighborhoods	not mentioned	generally positive, with around 67% of the participants demonstrating a good attitude towards UGI in their respective neighborhoods		The study's main contributions include improving understanding of residents' attitudes towards UGI and identifying strategies for developing more favorable attitudes towards green infrastructure	

Figure 2. Content analysis table for the selected 20 case studies. Created by the authors

The case studies reveal common challenges faced by green infrastructure projects in the Global South. Financial constraints are a pervasive issue, affecting the implementation, maintenance, and sustainability of these initiatives. Many projects struggle with funding shortages, which can hinder their success and longevity. Moreover, a lack of institutional capacity and support presents significant obstacles. Insufficient institutional capacity, poor coordination among stakeholders, and inadequate policy support can impede the effective planning and execution of green infrastructure projects. Governance and regulatory issues further complicate the situation, with fragmented responsibilities and unclear regulatory frameworks posing significant challenges to project implementation. Public perception and engagement also present challenges, particularly in areas with low awareness and economic constraints. Gaining public support and participation is crucial but often difficult, highlighting the need for strategies that engage diverse community groups and address their specific needs. Technical and logistical challenges are another common hurdle. The suitability of different types of green infrastructure and the complexities of integrating them into urban landscapes require careful

consideration and expertise. Addressing these technical issues is essential for the successful implementation of green infrastructure projects.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

The analysis of the 20 case studies highlights the crucial role of public perception and engagement in the success of green infrastructure projects in the Global South. Positive perceptions stem from strong community involvement, visible benefits, and well-maintained spaces. Conversely, economic pressures, lack of awareness, and competition for resources can result in negative views. Common challenges include financial constraints, insufficient institutional support, governance issues, and technical difficulties. To improve public engagement, inclusive strategies such as participatory planning, community consultations, and resident involvement are essential. These methods foster community ownership and long-term support. Increasing awareness through tailored communication can address specific community concerns and promote the benefits of green infrastructure. Projects should be designed to meet the socio-economic needs of low-income residents, providing tangible benefits that address livelihood concerns. Strengthening institutional capacity and support is critical. Better coordination among stakeholders, clear regulatory frameworks, and robust policy support are needed for effective project implementation and maintenance. Sustainable funding from diverse sources, including public-private partnerships, grants, and community-based financing, is necessary for long-term success. Investing in research and development to address technical challenges will enhance the integration of green infrastructure into urban landscapes. By addressing these issues, green infrastructure projects in the Global South can achieve better outcomes, supporting sustainable urban development and resilience to environmental challenges.

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